

eCHARGE
4DRIVERS

eCharge4Drivers

Dissemination and Communication
Strategy

www.echarge4drivers.eu

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
CPO	Charging Point Operator
EC	European Commission
EIG	External Interest Group
EMSP	ElectroMobility Service Providers
EV	Electric Vehicle
H2020	Horizon 2020
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Standardisation Organisation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LEV	Light Electric Vehicle
OG	Observers Group
URG	User Reference Group
V2G	Vehicle-to-Grid
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Communication and Dissemination Strategy is the project's guidance document for all dissemination and communication activities that will take place within the project. It should be seen as a living document that will be adapted and revised throughout the project and following the timeline provided in the document.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan identifies and describes the target groups for dissemination activities and explains how and through which dissemination channels they will be reached. It describes the main dissemination tools, which will be particularly important for outreach activities.

This strategy also identifies key initiatives and EU-funded projects to establish strategic alliances and collaboration mechanisms and defines the methodology for the establishment of the external interest groups that will play an important role in the transferability of the obtained results.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 About eCharge4Drivers

eCharge4Drivers is an H2020 project running from June 2020 to May 2024 and deployed by a consortium of 32 partners. Charging an electric vehicle (EV) is still not as convenient as refuelling a conventional vehicle, potentially posing a barrier to increase the market uptake of EVs. eCharge4Drivers works to substantially improve the EV charging experience within cities and for long trips. The project will develop and demonstrate user-friendly charging stations and innovative charging solutions as well as smart charging services for the users. By capturing users' perceptions and expectations on the various charging options and their mobility and parking habits, eCharge4Drivers will organise demonstrations in 10 areas across Europe, including metropolitan areas and Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T) corridors. Charging stations in these areas will offer user-friendly and convenient functionalities for EV drivers of passenger and light vehicles and motorcycles, such as direct payment methods and bigger, user-friendly displays. Using the knowledge generated, the project will also propose an EV Charging Location Planning Tool, fostering the broad implementation of charging infrastructure in Europe.

1.2 About the eCharge4Drivers Dissemination and Communication: enhancing impact

The European Commission defines the terms Dissemination and Communication as:

- **Dissemination** is the public disclosure of the results of the project in any medium. Disclosure may sound passive, like a shop opening up, but it is an activity, like a shopkeeper attracting customers. It is a process of promotion and awareness-raising right from the beginning of a project. It makes research results available to various stakeholder groups (like research peers, industry and other commercial actors, professional organisations, policymakers) in a targeted way, to enable them to use the results in their own work. This process must be planned and organised at the beginning of each project, usually in a dissemination plan.
- **Communication** means taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. The aim is to reach out to society as a whole and in particular to some specific audiences while demonstrating how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges.

The Dissemination and Communication strategy ensures that the activities and outputs of the eCharge4Drivers project are widely disseminated and made transferrable. Therefore, we have defined the following objectives:

- Maximise outreach and widely communicate eCharge4Drivers activities, benefits and outcomes to a wide range of stakeholders;
- Develop a Communication, awareness and dissemination strategy and a set of communication materials and tools;
- Set up the necessary channels to allow the on-going eCharge4Drivers communication;
- Organise the eCharge4Drivers events;

- Set up External Interest Groups, to enrich the knowledge on user needs and requirements and to facilitate the dissemination and transferability of the eCharge4Drivers products, methods, recommendations and guidelines;
- Coordinate the scientific outreach through the development of (open access) papers and participation in the external events;
- Liaise with relevant national and international projects, platforms, initiatives and standardisation working groups.

1.3 About this document

This document presents an overview of how the objectives, as mentioned above, will be achieved and, thus, provides the framework to guide communication and dissemination activities within eCharge4Drivers. It identifies and describes the target groups for dissemination and communication activities and explains how and through which dissemination channels they will be reached. It describes the main dissemination tools to be developed within the project and identifies project milestones which will be particularly important for the implementation of outreach activities. It also provides guidelines to eCharge4Drivers’ partners on their roles and actions to perform and assure effective communication of eCharge4Drivers’ objectives, activities and results.

It is important to note that this deliverable should be considered as a living document that will be adapted throughout the lifetime of the project. This will be done after two official reporting periods. An overview of the planned revision is presented in the table below:

Table 1 Planned revision of the deliverable 8.1

D8.1 developed and submitted	M4
Revision 1	M18-M20
Revision 2	M36-M38

Besides planned revisions, changes will be introduced to the document in case the need arises at any time of the project.

2 KEY GUIDING PRINCIPLES

To maximise the impact of the project activities and outcomes, we have adopted the following four key principles as presented in the figure below:

Figure 1 Key principles to guide the communication and dissemination activities in the eCharge4Drivers project

1. **Community building & cross-fertilisation:** This comprises all the dissemination and communication actions that will make the results and products of the project available to the interested stakeholders and the wider audience. It includes the following pillars:
 - A. Networking and Synergies
 - B. Publications
 - C. Events
 - D. External Interest Groups.

All of the four pillars will be explained in detail in section 7.
2. **Exploitable results:** Once the results are made available to the external world, partners will ensure that they are used and fully deployed when the project is finished. An exploitation plan will collect the expectations of the partners and assess the potential uptake of the outcomes by external players ascribable to the EVs and the charging infrastructure sector. A detailed exploitation plan will be presented in deliverable 9.4.
3. **User-centric awareness & communication:** The user-centric design of solutions with the end users in mind and ensuring their continuous engagement in the demonstrations is central for the design of a user-friendly infrastructure. To ensure this, the project foresees two levels of communication: local communications and national/European-level communication national. More information is provided in section 3 of this document.

4. **European Open Science:** eCharge4Drivers aims to support the European Union research, policy and regulation activities. Therefore, the knowledge, information and data generated by the project must be as exploitable and accessible by third parties external to the project. Their disclosure will be made taking into account the confidentiality of some data, necessary to protect the competitiveness of the business partners and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) force [1]. All public deliverables will be uploaded on the open source platform such as Zenodo. All scientific publications will be treated following the Open Access requirements.

3 TARGET GROUPS AND COMMUNICATION

3.1 Key message and project mission statement

One of the key work items of the project is to study and understand users' and stakeholders' concerns, perceptions and expectations with respect to different EV charging options. Based on this knowledge, the project will demonstrate user-friendly charging stations for passenger vehicles and Light Electric Vehicles (LEVs) and will enable the interoperability of end-to-end communication and the provision of interoperable services offering enhanced information about the charging process to the users.

To create an impact, these advancements in the charging experience will be widely communicated in targeted messages. We foresee two levels of communication:

- (1) the local level aimed at end users and
- (2) the national and EU level.

Local communication

Targeting EV drivers and local businesses

- To ensure the awareness of the impact and advancements developed for the end users
- To ensure the users' continuous engagement in the demonstrations.

This type of communication will be more publicity-oriented and tailored to each demonstration area, using the local language, with major input by the demonstration leaders and coordinated by Poliba.

Dissemination and communication at national and EU levels

Targeting policy makers at European and national levels, the European institutions and associations, the academic world and the global (electric) vehicle and charging infrastructure market.

POLIS (for the public sector), **ERTICO** (for the private sector), **Subject** (for the industrial sector) and **VUB** and **ICCS** (for the research sector) will lead the activities.

Since eCharge4Drivers addresses a wide array of target groups, formulating tailored messages is an important element of the project's communication activities. The defined messages will, therefore, be adapted based on the audience to which they are addressed and the communication channels that are used.

The baseline questions for this targeted communication are presented below:

- eCharge4Drivers studies and analyses the needs of EV users (and concerns of potential future EV users) so that charging solutions and services substantially improve the user charging experience.
- eCharge4Drivers develops and demonstrates charging solutions and services that can be user-friendly and innovative, improving the charging experience.
- eCharge4Drivers enables and demonstrates the interoperability of end-to-end communication (vehicle-to-charging station, charging station-to-back-end and back-end-to-

user) by implementing the common standards for vehicle-to-charger (ISO 15118) and charger-to-infrastructure communication (OCPP and IEC 63110).

3.2 Target groups

The project dissemination and impact creation will aim at targeting the following groups that are directly involved and concerned by the project results:

- **Current EV drivers:** the end-users, such as citizens of the eCharge4Drivers cities/regions who own or use (rented, shared, fleet vehicle) an EV, represent a primary target group of the local communication campaigns that will be developed by the cities in cooperation with the electromobility providers, intending to improve the user acceptance charging services.
- **Future EV drivers:** potential users, who do not yet possess or use an EV, represent also a primary target group of the local communication campaigns that will be developed by the cities in cooperation with the electromobility providers, intending to attract potential future EV drivers to use the technology with improved charging services.
- **Civil society representatives:** the target will be organisations that engage in electromobility, like car-clubs and e-mobility network organisations. They are organisations that can inform and represent the user groups of eCharge4Drivers and who can play a role at local level in influencing the attitude of end users.
- **Logistics operators and fleet managers:** communication will target these stakeholders to participate in the validation and assessment of project results and to encourage the usage of the knowledge created by the project to offer enhanced services, increasing user acceptance of charging services.
- **Local businesses:** businesses and institutions are an important vehicle-user group and will be targeted with local communication campaigns to improve the user acceptance of charging services, accelerate the deployment of electromobility and facilitate new business models.
- **Local and Regional Authorities/Urban Planners and Consultants:** within this group, special emphasis will be set on urban mobility professionals (e.g. local authorities staff and consultants) who currently lack knowledge regarding practical implementation paths for electric mobility and could benefit from the results of eCharge4Drivers.
- **E-Mobility Service Providers and Charging Point Providers:** the WP communication will target these stakeholders in eCharge4Drivers' cities, as well as in replication cities that are looking at future exploitation of eCharge4Drivers results and can feed the project with their know-how. The objective is to show these stakeholders how the project results can enhance their services and therefore increase their competitiveness, accelerating the implementation of electromobility. On the other side, the project will seek feedback and insights that can positively affect the project.
- **Vehicle manufacturers (OEMs):** the focus will be on organisations with the potential of implementing project results to offer better charging services to their users and improving the overall experience.
- **Energy Retailers / electric utilities:** the project will target this group to participate in the validation and assessment of project results. Communication will support targeting such organisations to plan the future deployment of electromobility in replication cities using eCharge4Drivers results.
- **Electricity Network Operators:** the project will target network operators of electricity grids by enabling grid-oriented smart charging concepts towards exploiting charging demand elasticity and enhancing the network EV hosting capacity.

- **Policy makers:** the communication will target policy makers at EU and national levels to share with them recommendations to cover the gaps and to harmonise regulatory frameworks in the EU countries in order to support the sustainable operation of charging infrastructure and accelerate the implementation of electromobility.
- **Standardisation working groups:** the communication will target standardisation bodies aiming to share with them potential standardisation gaps and ensure interoperability among diverse technologies and services.
- **Academia / Research Organisations:** the target will be institutions with the potential to integrate project results and findings in teaching activities, such as subjects for Master thesis or part of a Ph.D. thesis.

The table below explains in greater detail the target groups, their area and the instruments proposed to reach them:

Target groups	Target area	Key Message	Activities	Dissemination channels
Current EV drivers	Understandable by a large public of non-specialists	eCharge4drivers will improve the usability, access and interoperability of charging infrastructure	Presentation at local exhibitions, videos, news items, social media posts	Leaflets/flyers, social media, local media channels
Future EV drivers	Understandable by a large public of non-specialists	eCharge4drivers will solve the issues now faced by the EV drivers, so the experience can be as easy as with the conventional cars to which the drivers are used	Presentation at local exhibitions, videos, news items, social Media Posts	Leaflets/flyers, social media, local media channels
Citizens groups	Understandable by a large public of non-specialists	eCharge4drivers will improve the usability, access and interoperability of charging infrastructure	Presentation at local exhibitions, videos, news items, social media posts	Leaflets/flyers, social media, Website
Logistic Operators	Business	eCharge4Drivers will improve the charging experience with innovative user-friendly charging solutions and services	Presentation at local workshops and webinars, videos, news items, social media posts	Leaflets/flyers, social media, website, logistics outlets
Fleet Managers	Business	eCharge4Drivers will improve the charging experience with innovative user-friendly charging solutions and services	Presentation at local workshops and webinars, videos, news items, social media posts	Leaflets/flyers, social media, website, communication through the dedicated associations
Local Businesses	Understandable by a large public of non-specialists	eCharge4drivers will improve the usability, access and interoperability of charging infrastructure	Presentations at local workshops, videos, social media posts	Leaflets/flyers, social media, SME associations, local communication channels, ERTICO/POLIS
Local and Regional Authorities	Legislative	eCharge4Drivers developments will unlock the deployment of electromobility and will therefore improve the air quality in urban centres	Presentation at local workshops/webinars/conferences, news items, social media posts, press release	Leaflets/flyers, website, social media, newsletter, ERTICO/POLIS communication channels

Target groups	Target area	Key Message	Activities	Dissemination channels
eMSPs	Technical	eCharge4Drivers developments will allow a more sustainable and user-friendly expansion of their networks	Presentation at local workshops and webinars, news items, social media posts, final event	Website, social media, newsletter, dedicated associations
CPOs	Technical	eCharge4Drivers developments will allow a more sustainable expansion of their networks	Presentation at local workshops and webinars, News Items, Social Media Posts, Final Event	Website, social media, newsletter, associations, platforms such as Platform for Electromobility
Vehicle Manufacturers	Business	eCharge4Drivers will develop guidelines for the future implementation of Plug & Charge by vehicle manufacturers	Presentation at local workshops and webinars, News Items, Social Media Posts, Final Event	Website, social media, newsletter, industrial outlets
Energy retailers / Electric utilities	Technical/Business	eCharge4Drivers developments will improve the charging experience unlocking the deployment of electromobility in cities	Presentation at local workshops and webinars, news items, social media posts, final event	Website, social media, newsletter, associations like Eurelectrics
Urban Planners and Consultants	Technical/Scientific	eCharge4Drivers studies users' needs to improve the charging experience and demonstrates the interoperability of end-to-end communication	Publications, factsheets, presentation at webinars, social media posts, news items, final event	Leaflets/flyers, webinars, website, newsletter, local and European outlets
Electricity Network Operators	Technical/Business	eCharge4Drivers grid oriented smart charging concepts will enable the exploitation of EV charging demand flexibility towards efficient grid integration of EVs	Presentation at local workshops and webinars, News Items, Social Media Posts, Final Event	Website, social media, newsletter, associations like Eurelectrics.
Policy makers	Legislative	eCharge4Drivers developments will unlock the deployment of electromobility and will therefore improve the air quality in urban centres	Publications, factsheets, presentation at webinars and events, news items, press release, final event, social media posts	Website, social media, newsletter, synergies with the other relevant projects
Standardisation working groups	Standardisation	eCharge4Drivers developments will deploy and test e-mobility communication protocols for charging and payment services considering diverse technologies and services	Publications, factsheets, presentation at webinars and events, news items, press release, final event, social media posts	Website, social media, newsletter, direct contact through the relevant partners such as ABB, Idiada
Academia/	Scientific	eCharge4Drivers studies user needs to improve the	Publications, factsheets, final	Website, social media, newsletter,

Target groups	Target area	Key Message	Activities	Dissemination channels
Research Organisations		charging experience and demonstrates the interoperability of end-to-end communication	event, news items, social media posts, presentations at conferences/seminars	direct contacts through ICCS, VUB, Poliba.

Table 2 eCharge4Drivers Targeted Communication

3.3 Stakeholders database

A contact list of relevant stakeholders at local, regional, national and international levels is crucial to provide partners with easy methods of dissemination of all project outputs to the relevant target groups. Similarly, eCharge4Drivers will utilise all relevant international contacts available to the consortium partners to promote the project at local, regional, national and European levels.

An eCharge4Drivers contact database will be developed in the first year of the project and kept updated. This database will be part of the project's lasting legacy, as it will allow stakeholders to have a point of reference that can be enriched and updated for future eCharge4Drivers-related activities.

The following partners will make contributions to the Stakeholders Database:

- ERTICO will contribute by setting up a mailing list, through which stakeholders will be contacted and kept informed about eCharge4Drivers' latest developments. This database will be set up using the service called Mailchimp and will be compliant with the GDPR regulation (for more information see section 5.4 Newsletters).
- POLIS and ERTICO will include information about the project in their regular communication channels (e.g. e-bulletins, website and social media) allowing their readers to subscribe to the eCharge4Drivers mailing list and/or follow the project on social media.
- Project partners may also invite potentially interested contacts on a personal basis, but not via unsolicited mass mailings. Project partners will not add any stakeholder to the project contact database, but the stakeholders will be required to register themselves and will be informed on how their data will be used (only for information relating to this project).

4 PROJECT IDENTITY AND TEMPLATES

Online and offline communication will be a key part of the dissemination of the project activities, objectives and outputs to various target audiences. To support this effort, the following communication tools, dissemination material and publications will be developed in the context of the project.

4.1 Project Identity

4.1.1 Brand

eCharge4Drivers' brand is often the first thing people see when encountering the project. It represents our project, our personality and our appearance. It is important we ensure our brand integrity is always maintained.

The golden rule when using the eCharge4Drivers brand is to use it consistently and in-line with our guidelines and communication procedures because inconsistency leads to confusion and weakens the branding. Applying these guidelines correctly ensures that our messages are always clear, they reinforce each other and they always express the true character of the eCharge4Drivers brand. You can find the general dissemination procedures to refer to at this [link](#).

4.1.2 Project logo

A project logo was created in the first month of the project. This will ensure a visual identity for the project and help to build the brand and reputation of eCharge4Drivers.

eCharge4Drivers logo has two key elements: the icons and the written part. The different icons represent the electric vehicles and their integration into the urban public transport infrastructure. All icons are displayed on a bigger symbol (three curved lines and a dot) representing the Wi-Fi network. Green, one of the colours chosen for the project's logo, suggests the idea of "green" and sustainability, one of the core ideas behind eCharge4Drivers. The written part includes the project's name. Colours for the project are ERTICO Charcoal and ERTICO's 'Clean Mobility' focus colour, namely Pantone 447 C and Pantone 3258 C.

The logo has several options (positive and reversed included) for different uses, for different reproduction purposes (presentations, brochures, roll-ups, website etc.).

Figure 2 eCharge4Drivers logo positive and negative

The icon represents a vibrant mix of mobility services pointed directly at the individual user. The shape is dynamic and the colour range is exciting and energetic. The typography is simple, direct and bold. It is an engaging device that encompasses the eCharge4Drivers project.

4.1.3 Logo size and use

The master logo should always appear fully intact regardless of the size in which it is adapted. Each element and its position in relation to each other have been carefully designed and must never be stretched, altered or distorted.

4.1.4 Colours

The colour logo is made up of a range of colours, as illustrated in Figure 3. Users should always try to use the full colour logo on a white background. The reversed version of the full colour logo should only be used on ERTICO charcoal colour.

In situations where the logo must be reproduced in black and white, the one-colour logo should be used. In situations where the logo must appear on a dark coloured background, then the one-colour reversed logo should be used.

eCharge4Drivers' logo possesses a strong external recognition thanks to the use of a limited colour palette, composed of core and secondary colours, as illustrated in Figure 3:

ERTICO Charcoal	Focus: Clean Mobility	Secondary colours	
PANTONE 447 C	PANTONE 3258 C	PANTONE 367 C	PANTONE 284 C
C = 70 M = 60 Y = 60 K = 60	C = 65 M = 0 Y = 39 K = 0	C = 41 M = 0 Y = 68 K = 0	C = 59 M = 0 Y = 17 K = 0
R = 48 G = 52 B = 52	R = 69 G = 194 B = 177	R = 162 G = 207 B = 95	R = 106 G = 170 B = 228
#303434	# 45c2b1	# a4d65e	#6cace4

Figure 3 eCharge4Drivers logo colours

Core colours: Strong colours are used within the master logo. They can also be used carefully as highlight or background colours in documents.

Secondary colours: Any secondary colours should be chosen to neutrally compliment the Core colours and should be used sensitively with these colours. Users must always ensure that White and eCharge4Drivers' Core colours are more dominant.

4.1.5 Incorrect use

Never reproduce the logo on a coloured or textured background

Never distort or stretch the logo

Never place the elements in a different position from the original logo

Never enclose the logo in any kind of shape

Never alter the colours of the logo or reproduce the colours as tints

Never recreate the logo using a different typeface

Figure 4 Incorrect uses of eCharge4Drivers logo

4.1.6 Fonts

Our primary identity typeface is Avenir, to be used in all printed and web materials (PPT presentations, brochures, flyers and other promotional material, etc.).

We suggest using 10 of the 12 styles available, to be chosen according to the specific material and criteria of the designer.

As a basic rule for formatting texts, use Avenir Black. For subheadings, use Avenir Heavy. For body copy, use Avenir Light.

Avenir

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

1234567890,./=+&_€@!(%)\$|?>":

Mintur min corem quia etur?

TIUREPUDIS ET QUI BEATUS, ODITA SAM

Des que nimporio opta es que earcid utesequis ent, ut alitatem qui asit illesequisti alique lam estis maiorem. Itatem quuntem sam quae es simus atis reperatempa nonsequ iaspercimus doluptatae cullaccat eatum eum et est, utPellessi dolent, simoluptur, qui nus volupta quas isi in et essunto minte autem et ut provitium facitae odi debis ad ut vollupt atestrum dolores solupienis et ute nonecep erist, consedi temquia videllescil magnimp errorer ovidebi tiurepudis et qui beatus, odita sam, imaxim voloris nimi, culpa quos exerum as aut estiasp no.

For office materials (such as the content of official deliverables, press releases and other documents), use Arial. Body copy must be set at 11pt.

Arial Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890,./=+&_£@!(%)\$|?>”:

Arial Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890,./=+&_£@!(%)\$|?>”:

4.1.7 Slogan

By creating the slogan “**Easy charging, easy driving**”, the goal is to explain in a quick and effective way the function of the project. If charging of EVs is made simple, then driving will be much easier in terms of planning journeys and charging stops. This slogan is short and effective, and can therefore be repeated and included in all communications (online and printed) and be easily remembered by the general public.

4.2 Document templates

Templates have been created for official project documents to ensure a consistent and professional visual identity. Templates have been created for:

- Press releases
- PowerPoint presentations
- Agendas
- Meeting minutes
- Project deliverables

PRESS RELEASE

15 June 2020, Brussels
info@echarge4drivers.eu

Title

[Name of the company/organisation] is delighted to announce its participation in the eagerly awaited eCharge4Drivers project, officially launched in Athens, Greece on September 2018. eCharge4Drivers, is an EU-funded H2020 innovation action and consists of 21 partners from 9 EU countries, united in their vision to build a sustainable future for connected and automated vehicles.

The aim of eCharge4Drivers, coordinated by the Institute of Communication & Computer Systems (ICCS), is to provide the ICT infrastructure to enable the transition towards road transport automation. eCharge4Drivers is bringing together, adapting and improving technological advances from different industries, mainly the telecommunication, automotive and IT industries. The project adopts a hybrid communication approach where all the major wireless technologies, i.e. cellular, ITS G5 and LTE-V, are integrated under flexible "sliced" network architecture. This architecture will ensure performance and resilience for different groups of applications according to the needs of higher levels of automation. On top of that, a distributed IT environment for data aggregation and analytics will be implemented.

Quote from partner and comment on role.

[Please avoid the use of terms as WPx, Taskx as these are not understandable by the public.]

The result of this allows seamless integration and the exchange of data and services between all the different actors, encouraging third parties to develop, deliver and provide innovative services, thus creating new business opportunities. Cyber-security and data privacy aspects will be considered throughout the entire ICT infrastructure. In addition, innovative accurate localisation services, exploiting the cellular network and information from other sources, such as on-board sensors, especially in complex areas (e.g. urban), will be addressed. Standardisation and interoperability are of high interest within eCharge4Drivers in order to ensure the project facilitates the transition to higher levels of automation. In this context, issues related to the frequency spectrum will be investigated, and with the organisation of relevant workshops the engagement of policy makers and public authorities will be

PRE-RELEASE | eCharge4Drivers | Partner Name

To achieve its objectives eCharge4Drivers, instead of working in generic solutions with questionable impact, it builds on four specific high-value use cases (urban and highway) which will be demonstrated and validated under real-life conditions at the project test sites in Austria, Germany, Italy and across the Italian-Austrian border.

For more information, please contact [\[add partners details here\]](#)

End

EDITOR NOTES

About the project eCharge4Drivers is a 4-year project of 14 million euros co-financed by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Programme. It demonstrates additional convenient charging options for Electric Vehicles (EVs) within cities, a mobile charging service, charge points at lamp posts, networks of battery swapping stations for light EVs and a transportable charging station service to cover temporary needs in 11 areas across Europe, including metropolitan areas and Trans-European (TEN-T) corridors. The project partners are: ICCS, ABB, ABEE, BMW, BFS, ROBERT BOSCH (RB), BARCELONA DE SERVEIS MUNICIPALS SA, CEA, CHARGERY, CRF, ELECTRONAPS, ERTICO, GAM, GREENPACK, HUBJECT, ICOP, IDIADA, MOSAIC, NEXTLAB, SCUTUM, POJUS, POLIBA, POWERDALE, ROUTE220, OTS, SMATRICS, UNIPI, UoS, VERBUND, VCC, VUB and ZES.

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 875131 (Innovation Action)

About the partner

Contact us

Figure 5 Press release template

Figure 6 PowerPoint template

AGENDA

Type name of event here

15–17 July 2020

Venue: Name of venue. city

**For each presentation, at least 10 minutes should be left in each case for discussion. Attendance is compulsory and all must stay till the end of the meeting.*

Day 1: 15 July 2020, Wednesday

Time	Description	Presenter(s)
00:00 – 01:00	Welcome	ERTICO
00:00 – 01:00	Objectives	ERTICO, Other
00:00 – 01:00	Etc	Other
00:00 – 01:00	LUNCH BREAK	
00:00 – 01:00	Free discussion	ERTICO
00:00 – 01:00	Workshop	ERTICO, Other
00:00 – 01:00	Recommendation	Other

AGENDA | Name of event

00:00 – 01:00	<p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Cras facilisis nisi id consectetur.</p> <p>4. List item</p> <p>5. List item</p> <p>6. List item</p>	Other
00:00 – 01:00	COFFEE BREAK	
00:00 – 01:00	Content	ERTICO
00:00 – 01:00	Content	ERTICO, Other
00:00 – 01:00	Content	Other
00:00 – 01:00	LUNCH BREAK	
00:00 – 01:00	Content	ERTICO
00:00 – 01:00	Content	ERTICO, Other
00:00 – 01:00	Content	Other
00:00 – 01:00	COFFEE BREAK	
00:00 – 01:00	Content	ERTICO
00:00 – 01:00	Content	ERTICO, Other
00:00 – 01:00	Content	Other
00:00 – 01:00	END OF DAY 2	

Day 3: 17 July 2020, Friday

Time	Description	Presenter(s)
------	-------------	--------------

Figure 7 Agenda template

MEETING MINUTES

Type name of meeting here

15–17 July 2020

Brussels, Belgium

Title	
Status	
Version Number	1.0
Dissemination Level	
Document Date	dd/mm/yyyy

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 875131 (Innovation Action)

MEETING MINUTES | eCharge4Drivers

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Insert minute heading here	3
Insert minute heading here	3
Insert minute heading here	3
Day 3 > 20 July 2020	3
Insert minute heading here	3

Figure 8 Meeting minutes template

Deliverable Ref

Deliverable name

Work Package	
Task 1.3	
Authors	X.Y.
Dissemination Level	
Status	
Due date	dd/mm/yyyy
Document Date	dd/mm/yyyy
Version Number	1.0

Quality Control

	Name	Organisation	Date
Editor	dd/mm/yyyy	Name	dd/mm/yyyy
Peer review 1			dd/mm/yyyy
Peer review 2			dd/mm/yyyy
Authorised by (Technical Coordinator)			dd/mm/yyyy
Authorised by (Quality Manager)			dd/mm/yyyy
Submitted by (Project Coordinator)			dd/mm/yyyy

Figure 9 Deliverable template

All templates have been made available to project partners via dedicated online workspace (Redmine).

Project partners can add their logo to the original PPT but should check with ERTICO before presenting. Furthermore, partners should inform ERTICO of where and when presentations will be given.

A standard presentation will be developed based on the template with input received by all work package leaders, taking responsibility for their respective work packages and led by ERTICO.

4.3 Visual Identity Notices/Disclaimer

As the project is co-funded by the European Union, dissemination, communication and publication materials must clearly acknowledge the receipt of EU funding through:

- The display of the EU flag
- The following text referring to Horizon2020: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 875131”.

A disclaimer will also be included on the website, stating:

“eCharge4Drivers is co-funded by the EU under the H2020 Research and Innovation Programme (grant agreement No 875131). The content of this website reflects solely the views of its authors. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The eCharge4Drivers consortium members shall have no liability for damages of any kind that may result from the use of these materials.”

Any publication or any other material prepared by the consortium members, even if at national level, on behalf of eCharge4Drivers and in the framework of their assigned tasks in the project, shall at least display the project logo and EU flag and funding statement.

5 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL

5.1 Project leaflet

An initial leaflet will be produced for the first year of the project and will then be updated when and if necessary, throughout eCharge4Drivers' lifespan. The leaflet will introduce eCharge4Drivers and its key objectives, and follow the project's visual and branding guidelines. It will serve as promotion tool during conferences and events and will be made available online for download. Each consortium member will be provided with a number of leaflets depending on their requirements (expected event attendance or other distribution needs).

5.2 Brochure and posters

A general project brochure will be produced at the end of the project to summarise the final results. Furthermore, technical posters will be created as needed for events. Posters in different languages will be created where needed for events aimed at national audiences.

5.3 Banners

A general roll-up banner will be provided to brand eCharge4Drivers at events. Digital graphics and banners of different sizes (to fit on social media, documents and email signatures) will also be prepared for use in specific exhibitions, conferences and events, and made available on the project's website and consortium's online work space.

5.4 Newsletters

At least twice yearly, electronic newsletters will be issued to ensure a regular flow of information to all interested stakeholders. A newsletter subscription form will also be added at the project website.

All partners are invited to make contributions for content to the newsletter. However, to facilitate the process of collecting information, ERTICO, ICCS and POLIS have created a set of internal rules and distributed it to eCharge4Drivers' consortium via the project's online workspace (Redmine). The aim of this document is to effectively collect news and/or presentations, avoiding overlaps of items and making an efficient use of time and resources.

E-Newsletters will be one of the main engaging tools for eCharge4Drivers. E-newsletters will be advertised on the website and the project's social media platforms. Such communication tool will follow the project's branding guidelines and will be GDPR compliant (users will have to actively opt in or opt out in order to subscribe/unsubscribe from eCharge4Drivers' news and their data will be stored for a specific amount of time). E-Newsletters will be issued twice per year. In case of generation of more content, more e-newsletters can be foreseen. Such tool will also be useful to monitor the project's trend and readership behaviour, and adjust the communication accordingly.

5.5 Promotional materials (branded pens, bags, etc.) for event

To maximise its presence and fully brand eCharge4Drivers at events and meetings, ERTICO will produce a set of materials, gadgets and giveaways to distribute to attendees and participants on site. Promotional material can range from branded pens to branded notebooks, pins, stickers, USB keys, etc. ERTICO will consult in due time with POLIS and ICCS to decide on the most suitable gadget to produce for future events where eCharge4Drivers will be presented. The gadget that will be produced for eCharge4Drivers' final event will be in line with the project's goal and try to transmit the core functionality of the project. Also, in this occasion, ERTICO will liaise with POLIS and ICCS to decide on the most suitable gadget to create and represent the project.

5.6 Animated video design and production

Around the second year of the project, ERTICO will produce a video or an animated video to promote eCharge4Drivers and raise awareness of the project. The video will be published on eCharge4Drivers' website, YouTube channel (separate channel or one of the partners) and disseminated on eCharge4Drivers' social media, as well as shared with the project's consortium to amplify the outreach. The video will be structured taking into account the intended audience described in the communication strategy and particularly target user groups.

6 ONLINE MEDIA

6.1 eCharge4Drivers website

The website will serve as the main source of information for the project. The eCharge4Drivers project website will be constantly updated and will provide all information on the evolution of the project, including objectives, partners, methodologies, results, publications, news, events and success stories. The website will also include links to eCharge4Drivers social media channels. ERTICO will lead on content generation, with all partners providing suggestions for content.

More detailed information on eCharge4Drivers' website can be found in D.8.2 "eCharge4Drivers website".

6.2 Social media

Key social media platforms will be used to enhance the online presence of the project. These channels will be used to engage with both professional communities and the general public. The project will use two social media channels to communicate and engage with users: Twitter and LinkedIn.

6.2.1 Twitter

A Twitter profile has been set up following the project's visual identity and identifying the most influential hashtags in the field of transport and electric vehicles. Twitter will play a key role in supporting the communications objectives of eCharge4Drivers. The Twitter account will be used to raise awareness for the project and showcase eCharge4Drivers activities and events. The language of the account will be English, however, occasional posts in the project local languages will be allowed when needed, especially in order to build a networking in each demonstration area.

The Twitter account audience will be general public, other EU projects, EVs community, European institutions, stakeholders and various professionals. The idea behind this channel is to reach a large number of followers from different backgrounds interested in the project and in charging solutions, electromobility and sustainable transport in Europe.

Tweets will contain:

- Latest news from the project
- Activities from meetings or workshops
- Activities from pilots
- Retweets of related twitter accounts of initiatives, partners, cities, projects and events

ICCS will manage the project Twitter account and will ensure to update content in a regular basis. Nevertheless, all partners are expected to send relevant content for Twitter and support the promotion of eCharge4Drivers social media accounts by sharing, liking and retweeting. The administrator of the account will be also committed to follow and be followed by relevant audience (e.g. partners social media accounts, EU stakeholders, relevant EU projects, EU institutions, scientific research organisations etc.).

Main keywords and hashtags (such as #ElectricVehicles, #chargingexperience, #EV, #electromobility, #refueling, #chargingservices, #sustainability, #UserExperience, #usercentric, #EUGreenDeal) will also be used in order to increase the tweets' visibility.

The tweets will contain audio-visual elements (photos, videos) if it fits more effectively to the post content. All the project posts and tweets will be automatically published on the website's home page through a social stream.

The eCharge4Drivers Twitter account is @Charge4E and can be found here: <https://twitter.com/Charge4E>.

6.2.2 LinkedIn

A LinkedIn company page has also been set up following the project's visual identity and will communicate and engage with users by regularly posting content. LinkedIn will play an important role in disseminating information on the project in professional networks. The LinkedIn account will allow a large group of stakeholders but also end users to interact with the project and follow up on eCharge4Drivers developments, serving at the same time as a tool for the dissemination of activities and events.

The LinkedIn page will be public, rather than a private group.

The project LinkedIn page will be managed by ICCS which will ensure that posts will be published regularly. POLIS, ERTICO and all partners will provide suggestions for content.

The main purposes of eCharge4Drivers posts on the project LinkedIn page are the following:

- Spread information about the project and the current activities,
- Maintain a professional and up-to-date profile,
- Share and promote interesting scientific and industrial developments and events to the community,
- Liaise with other projects and initiatives.

The main language will be English and additional language posts will be shared in order to reach specific objectives.

The eCharge4Drivers LinkedIn profile can be found at <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eCharge4Drivers-project/>.

Both social media platforms will allow the project to gather statistics (outreach, followers, likes, etc) in specific periods of time and to serve as reflector of the website: the information published on eCharge4Drivers' website can be shared on these two social media platforms, amplifying the outreach. In addition, both social media platforms will engage with the project's consortium and identified groups of stakeholders by following and mentioning them, maximising the project's visibility and outreach.

6.3 Press releases

At important project milestones, press releases will be issued and sent to local press and, when relevant, to European and national press. Partners will be encouraged to communicate in national language with the local press to inform local citizens of what is happening. A standard press release template has been created, which can then be adapted to the local level. Press releases translated into local languages should be sent to POLIS Network for project records.

[The first press release](#) has been issued immediately after the Kick-off meeting of the project. It has been translated in local languages and published in local media.

PRESS RELEASE

17 June 2020, Brussels
info@echarge4drivers.eu

Member logo
goes here

Improving EV charging experience to speed up electric mobility revolution

New eCharge4Drivers project will enhance EV user experience at electric vehicle charging stations by offering improved services

[Name of company/organisation] 17th June 2020 - Today sees the launch of the new eCharge4Drivers project. The project will deliver enhanced user experience at electric vehicle charging stations by offering new, improved services, helping to increase the attractiveness and convenience of EVs. Working with 32 partners across 11 European countries, eCharge4Drivers will bring together key stakeholders help to offer an enhanced EV charging experience and speed up the transition to electric vehicles across Europe.

Sales of electric vehicles (EVs) are increasing rapidly across Europe. However, drivers still often encounter problems in finding appropriate charging options, limiting the ease of use of EVs and potentially posing a barrier to increase the uptake of EVs.

eCharge4Drivers aims to substantially improve the EV charging experience within cities and for long trips. By capturing users' perceptions and expectations on the various charging options and their mobility and parking habits, eCharge4Drivers will develop and demonstrate pilot projects in 10 areas across Europe, including metropolitan areas and Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T) corridors. Charging stations in these areas will offer user-friendly and convenient functionalities for EV drivers of passenger vehicles, motorcycles and light vehicles, such as direct payment methods and bigger, user-friendly displays.

Dr. Angelos Amditis, eCharge4Drivers Project Coordinator and Research Director of ICCS, said:

"The eCharge4Drivers project brings together 32 of the most important European electromobility actors with the aim to develop appropriate solutions to significantly improve the overall user experience when charging electric vehicles, and thus promoting the wide adoption of electromobility, following the ambitions of the European Green Deal towards a zero-emission transport system."

"Through eCharge4Drivers, we are in fact improving the autonomy of the electric vehicles, a factor that plays a decisive role in EVs wider and more efficient deployment, while also facilitating the design and development of smart charging infrastructure and enhanced interoperable services, offering additional incentives for choosing to purchase an electric car."

PRESS RELEASE | eCharge4Drivers | Partner Name

eCharge4Drivers will offer an enhanced experience for EV drivers by providing more sophisticated services to users before, during and after the charging process, including services for smart charging. The project will demonstrate additional convenient charging options within cities, a mobile charging service, charge points at lamp posts and networks of battery-swapping stations for LEVs.

Using the knowledge generated, the project will propose an EV Charging Location Planning Tool to determine the optimum mix of charging options to cover all user needs, as well as recommendations for legal and regulatory harmonisation, and guidelines for investors and authorities for the sustainability of charging infrastructure and services.

eCharge4Drivers was launched during an online Kick-Off Meeting, over two days from 16-17 June 2020. The consortium brings together 32 partners from 11 European countries.

OPTIONAL. Quote from your organisation. Commenting on the launch of the project and the role of your organisation within eCharge4Drivers

EDITOR NOTES

About the project eCharge4Drivers is a 4-year project of 14 million euros co-financed by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Programme. It demonstrates additional convenient charging options for Electric Vehicles (EVs) within cities, a mobile charging service, charge points at lamp posts, networks of battery swapping stations for light EVs and a transportable charging station service to cover temporary needs in 11 areas across Europe, including metropolitan areas and Trans-European (TEN-T) corridors. The project partners are: ICCS, ABB, ABE, BMW, BPS, ROBERT BOSCH (RB), BARCELONA DE SERVEIS MUNICIPALS SA, OEA, CHARGERLY, CRF, ELECTROMAPS, ERTICO, GAM, GREENPACK, HUBJECT, ICOOR, IDIADA, MOSAIC, NEXTLAB, SCUTUM, POLIS, POLIBA, POWERDALE, ROUTE20, OTS, SMATRICS, UNIP, UoS, VERBUND, VCC, VUB and ZES.

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 875131 (Innovation Action)

About the partner **Include a short description of your organisation – OPTIONAL, but suggested in case PR is published outside your organisation**

Contact us
Project Coordinator
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Project Manager
Dr. Evangelia Portouli: v.portouli@iccs.gr

Communication and Dissemination Coordinators
Sabina Asanova: SAsanova@polisnetwork.eu
Jamie Wylie: jwylie@polisnetwork.eu

Figure 10 The first project press release

7 COMMUNITY BUILDING AND CROSS-FERTILISATION

7.1 Networking and synergies

Stakeholders liaison. POLIS, ERTICO and the rest of the partners will exploit their extensive relevant contacts across Europe, from different sectors (public institutions, research, industry, consultants) and from different levels (European, national, regional and local).

A stakeholder database as described in section 3.3 will be created and it will be the responsibility of each consortium partner to populate the database with their relevant contacts and to attract more stakeholders by communicating about the project in their respective communication and dissemination activities. In addition, each of the partners will invite the readers of their communication channels to subscribe to the eCharg4Drivers newsletters, social media channels and website updates.

POLIS and ERTICO, two member-based organisations and co-leaders of the dissemination and communication activities, will communicate widely on the project among their members. POLIS will update on the developments of the project in the Working Group on Clean Vehicles and Air Quality. This will be done during the bi-annual meetings. Moreover, the synergies with the WG activities will be sought. ERTICO will communicate to its 110+ partners in the public and private sector as well as via its open communication platforms (e.g. Newsroom site at <https://erticonetwork.com>) and thematic webinars developed under the ERTICO Academy banner. It will also communicate via the platforms of other related clean and urban mobility activities, including the technical eMI3 working platform: Electro-Mobility ICT Interoperability Innovation Group (<https://emi3group.com>).

Cross-fertilisation and collaboration with other EU projects. The objective of this activity area is to support the cross-fertilisation via clustering and liaising with other relevant R&D projects funded under H2020 and other European-funded programmes (INTERREG, CEF, etc.) in the domain of electromobility and EV charging infrastructure. The project will carefully take into consideration the results of past projects (i.e. NeMo, ELIPTIC), to capitalise the lessons learned and avoid replications. Thanks to the support of networks and platforms, such as POLIS and ERTICO, the project will share plans, intermediate results and methodologies with other projects representatives, in order to benefit from possible mutual learning among projects and generating further cooperation and synergies among project actions.

Identified Projects

- ELVITEN
- ASSURED
- GreenCharge
- INCIT-EV
- SOLUTIONSplus
- USER-CHI
- CleanMobilEnergy
- NeMo

- OSMOSE
- ELIPTIC
- SmartCEM
- DHRT2
- UNIT-E
- EVA+
- Ultra-E
- SYNERG-E
- E-Via Flex-e

This overview is by no means exhaustive. The continuous exercise within the project will be to seek further synergies with the existing and future projects, to be Smarten funded in next year 2021.

Liaison with external networks and initiatives will be established with:

- *Stakeholders in the policy field:* e-Forum, European Green Vehicle Initiative, ACEA (European Automobile Manufacturers' Association), UITP, ERTRAC Working Groups, EGVI – European Green Vehicles Initiative, FIA, IRU, ALICE, eMI3 and the Sustainable Transport Forum, an expert group set by the EC to help the implementation of the Alternative Fuels Directive.
- *Stakeholders in the field of standardisation:* The project partners (ABB, Hubject, IDIADA, POLIS, ERTICO, BMW, VCC) will exchange knowledge with standardisation working groups where they are members, including CharIN, IEC 61851-23, ISO 15118, WG 63119, IEC 63110, to share information, guide the project technical work and maximise the outreach of its findings.
- *Academic and industrial stakeholders:* Workshops, conferences, seminars, industry and academia events will be attended by the project partners to deepen the impact of eCharge4Drivers' research into the academic world, industry symposia and among interested practitioners and relevant stakeholders. Examples of significant events for eCharge4Drivers participation include: TRA, TRB meetings, ITS World and European Congress, International Transport Forum, WCTRS, POLIS and EURO CITIES Conferences, CIVITAS Forum, SUMP Conference, International Transport Forum, EU Mobility Week, EU Green Week, European Utility Week, UITP European Mobility Exhibition, e-Mobility Stakeholder Forum and Intercharge Network Conference.

7.2 Publications

Publications include peer-reviewed scientific journals, trade journals and conference publications.

To assist partners in planning their dissemination activities, a list including relevant conferences, journals and magazines (which provide opportunities for disseminating the project via publications) will be created and will be available for all the partners as a google spreadsheet. It will be uploaded on the internal project repository platform Redmine. This living document will be regularly updated to include further dissemination opportunities, while relevant information will be sent to the consortium on a regular basis via direct mailing. The list of accepted and submitted partner publications will be also maintained and updated. Open Access (OA) guidelines for scientific publications and research data will be followed during the development of the publications as well as after the release of the documents,

ensuring FAIR principles [2] are being respected. eCharge4Drivers project will comply with all the H2020 OA requirements.

Peer-reviewed scientific journals, trade journals and conferences publications

Publications will be made in scientific journals and conference proceedings, so that they can easily reach the academic community. Moreover, articles will be presented in trade journals and magazines with the aim of presenting eCharge4Drivers evolution to end users.

eCharge4DriversDemos Factsheets. Based on the ELTIS case study template, two-pages factsheets will be produced to clearly describe the eCharge4Drivers activities demonstrated in each area, highlighting their relevance in specific transport contexts, their implementation, their results and the potential challenges. Factsheets will be conceived as operational inspirational material for local authorities and other stakeholders and will be made available in the national language of each demonstration area, as well as in English. The lead partner of each demonstrator will be in charge of developing the factsheets with the activities carried out in each demonstration area with input collected from the participant partners.

Demonstration area	Lead partner
Barcelona	B:SM
Grenoble	GAM
Berlin	Chargery
Luxembourg	Nexxtlab
Zellik/Brussels	VUB
Metropolitan city of Bari	POLIBA
Austria	SMATRICS
Northern Italy	Route220
Greece	BFS
Turkey	ZES
Cross-border	Hsubject

Table 3 eCharge4Drivers Demo site factsheet responsibilities

7.3 Events

eCharge4Drivers plans to organise its own dissemination events as well as take advantage of other established events to present project results to a wider audience, including those events organised by the partners. The list of identified international conferences and related events organised by project partners and external partners where eCharge4Drivers may present is illustrated in the table below.

Partner's name	Date	Activity's name	Location	Event's website/webpage link	Partner's contribution (select from list)	Audience type	Audience type (select from list)	Estimated number of	PPT or other material	Activity Status (select from list)	Details/comments (please use)
2020											
ICCS	4-8 October 2020	ITS World Congress	Virtual	https://www.itsworldcongress.com/	Speaker during a session	Policy Makers, Industry, Government	Policy Makers	Virtual event		Planned	*User-Centric and
ICCS/ERTICO	tbd	ELVITEN Final Event								Planned	
ICCS	September - 2 October 2020	EV Charging Infrastructure 4	Virtual	https://www.mmaexpo.com/	Speaker during a session	Industry	Policy Makers	Virtual event		Planned	Planned session
POLIS	21 October 2020	Online Workshop in the fra	Virtual	https://europa.eu/rapid/	Speaker during a session	Policy Makers, Industry, S	Policy Makers	about 50 (virtual event)		Planned	This workshop wi
	Sep-20	EU Mobility Week	Pan-European Event	https://mobilityweek.eu/home/		Civil Society, Users		>1000		Identified (tbc)	
	Oct-20	Green Week	Lisbon/EU/Virtual	https://www.eugreenweek.eu/en/		Policy makers, Civil Society, Users		>1000		Identified (tbc)	
ERTICO	9-10 Nov 2020	ITS Virtual European Congres	Virtual	https://itseuropeancongress.com/	Organizer	Policy, industry, academia		TBC		Identified (tbc)	
2021											
	June 2021	Urbanism Next Europe	Rotterdam, The Netherlands	https://europe.urbanismnext.org/						Identified (tbc)	
	October 2021	ITS World Congress	Hamburg, Germany	https://www.itsworldcongress2020.com/		Industry, Policy Makers, OEMs		>1000		Identified (tbc)	
	December 2021	UITP Global Transport Summit	Melbourne, Australia	https://uitpsummit.org/		Industry, Policy Makers, OEMs		>1000		Identified (tbc)	
	December 2021	POLIS conference	tbd			Policy Makers				Identified (tbc)	
	Nov-Dec 2021	European Utility Week (Enl)	Milan	https://www.enl-europe.com		Industry, OEMs, Policy makers				Identified (tbc)	
	2021	Urban Mobility Days	tbd	http://www.eumod.org/		Policy makers, Civil Society				Identified (tbc)	
tbd		UITP European Mobility exhi	tbd			Industry, Policy Makers, OEMs		>1000		Identified (tbc)	
tbd		e-Mobility stakeholder forum	tbd							Identified (tbc)	
tbd		Interchange Network Confere	tbd	https://www.intercharge-network-conference.com/						Identified (tbc)	
tbd		IRA conference	tbd	https://iraconference.eu/		Policy Makers, Industry, Scientific Community				Identified (tbc)	
tbd		EUROCITIES conference	tbd							Identified (tbc)	
tbd		EU Mobility Week	Pan-European Event	https://mobilityweek.eu/home/		Civil Society, Users		>1000		Identified (tbc)	
tbd		Green Week	tbd	https://www.eugreenweek.eu/en/		Policy makers, Civil Society, Users		>1000		Identified (tbc)	
tbd		International Transport Forum	Leipzig	https://2021.itf-oecd.org/		Policy Makers				Identified (tbc)	
ERTICO	11-15 October 2021	ITS World Congress	Hamburg, Germany	https://itsworldcongress.com/		Industry, Policy Makers, OEMs		>1000			
2022											
	December 2022	POLIS conference				Policy Makers				Identified (tbc)	
2023											

Table 4 Preliminary eCharge4Drivers Events List

eCharge4Drivers will organise several events throughout its lifetime, in order to raise stakeholder awareness about its goals and objectives, to provide guidance on its developments and demonstration activities and to disseminate its results among relevant stakeholders. The events will take different shapes:

- Awareness activities (including webinars) will be organised when the demonstrations are ready to start. Main target: end users and local stakeholders.
- Local workshops will take place in the demonstration areas of the project, to showcase the new charging systems and services integrated in the different areas and to promote the project among end users and interested stakeholders. Main target: end users and European stakeholders.
- A final event will be organised to present the outcomes and findings of the project and to prepare the ground for further developments and exploitation.

Communication and dissemination actions are an important pillar of the eCharge4Drivers project and the consortium will ensure that the action will be delivered despite the challenges created by the COVID-19 pandemic. In particular, in the first phase of the project, this will lead to an even stronger emphasis on a digital format. A certain degree of flexibility should be shown in the current situation. Dissemination and communication co-leaders, as well as the consortium partners, have shown great resilience as well as a high degree of adaptability. POLIS and ERTICO have further built experience of translating physical events into high-quality online events and therefore will apply their knowledge as long as the situation will not allow to organise physical meetings. Once the pandemic ceases, the events, meetings, site visits and workshops in the framework of the dissemination and communication actions will go to the physical format.

7.3.1 Outreach to local stakeholders (ICCS/POLIS)

Targeted communication at the demonstration sites will be achieved through different activities. A generic launch campaign will be designed, involving digital media, launch events

and press activities (e.g. press releases, press conference, setting up interviews with local partners for electronic and printed media). Local partners will translate the communication material into the local language and promote it to on-site media.

Local workshops will also take place in the demonstration areas of the project, to showcase the new charging systems and services integrated in the different areas. In order to facilitate the communication procedures of the workshops, there will be constant contact between the involved partners and continuous assistance in identifying the local stakeholders.

7.3.2 Ensuring users' continuous engagement in the demonstrations (ICCS)

Local demonstration partners, coordinated by Poliba WP5 leader and supported by POLIS and ERTICO, will be responsible for awareness and communication activities at local level, identifying and organising the communication and promotion actions to be performed to reach the relevant target groups. This will include communication campaigns in national language and awareness sessions for end users as regards the charging systems and services demonstrated in each area. The aim of these campaigns is to continuously raise users' awareness about the demonstrations and enhance their engagement. For this reason, the communication strategy will be primarily based on social media, identifying the relevant channels and activities to ensure that the project engages effectively with all stakeholders.

7.4 Activity registers and Dissemination procedure

Three dissemination registers have been set up on Google Spread sheets:

1. Events
2. Other activities
3. Publications

All activities for these categories should be recorded on a regular basis in these registers.

The participation of consortium partners in any event with an opportunity for dissemination and promotion of eCharge4Drivers (conferences, workshops, etc.), as well as the performance of every dissemination activity related to eCharge4Drivers (presentations, paper submissions, material distribution etc.), has to be communicated beforehand to ERTICO, ICCS, POLIS and the management team.

7.4.1 Step by step procedure

1. When an opportunity is identified, please notify the dissemination management team of your intention **at least 15 working days in advance**, specifying the details of the activity (type of activity, date, title, audience) and your role in it related to the eCharge4Drivers project (presenter, organiser, speaker in a session, author etc.). Prior notice is needed to update the Upcoming Event section of the eCharge4Drivers website and to allow cross-checking for overlaps and conflicts. Register the activity in the dedicated Dissemination Register, specifying all the details regarding the activity, as indicated in each column of the file (stakeholders, impact etc.);

2. The communication and dissemination leader (Polis) sends the request within 2 days to the Steering Committee members for approval, modification, request for extra information/clarifications or rejection.
3. The Steering Committee members have to reply to the communication and dissemination leader within 10 calendar days; no response is considered as an approval.
4. The communication and dissemination leader informs the initiator of the dissemination activity and the Project Coordinator about the decision.

In case of **Approval**

The initiator may proceed with the submission or realisation of the planned dissemination activity.

5. After your participation, send a short abstract (content of the session/presentation/discussion, quotes from speakers, highlights, relevant information related to eCharge4Drivers, size and type of audience reached) to ERTICO, ICCS and POLIS to update the News section of the website.

In case of **Conflict or objection**

6. The WP Leader(s), after consultation with the dissemination management team and in collaboration with the coordinator, can reject the proposed activity if it/they has/have objections related to overlaps or possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information concerning the work performed in the different WPs. In case of conflict, the dissemination management team and the involved partners will further discuss.

*If a conflict is created or further material is needed, then ERTICO, ICCS and POLIS will inform the partner that modifications or additions are required. Then the material is proposed again **within 5 working days** to the dissemination management team and the respective Task Leader and if significant changes (that might provoke conflicts among partners' interests) must be made, the previous procedure is followed.*

7.4.2 Dissemination activities report

Within **5 working days** after the implementation of the approved dissemination activity, the partner should fill in the [Dissemination Register](#) and store the dissemination material (final paper, presentation, poster etc.) in the dedicated folder set up in the collaboration tool.

If possible, the Partner should provide the Task Leader with **at least two photos** of their participation to the event/conference/workshop to feed the eCharge4Drivers website and collect relevant material to use throughout the project implementation.

NOTE:

- If the content is for an external meeting or for publication, but the same material has already been approved and presented elsewhere, the procedure should still be followed. This is to make sure that the WP8 Leader is informed of any additional change to the material, or if the material has remained unchanged. The approval would normally be expected as default, unless there was a change in circumstances or if other partners felt the particular event or publication forum (website, etc.) was somehow not suitable for our project.
- In case a partner wishes to organise a workshop or special event related to eCharge4Drivers, the approval of the dissemination management team is needed **3 months** before the realisation of this dissemination activity.
- GDPR: If the material contains a reference to other partners or the name or photo of an individual, publishing this content should be agreed with the person/partner in question before the dissemination request is made.
- Language: If the material is in a national language other than English, the procedure should still be followed. A brief description in English should be added (not a complete translation). Any other partners who understand the same language are especially invited to comment.

7.4.3 Acknowledgment

There are three types of acknowledgments that have to be added depending on the type of materials produced:

1. The following acknowledgement text should be included in **all publications related to the eCharge4Drivers work**:

“This work is a part of the eCharge4Drivers project. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 875131. This content reflects only the authors’ view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information this publication contains.”

2. For **other communication activities**, please add the EC emblem (flag) [available here](#), with the following sentence:

“This work is a part of the eCharge4Drivers project. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 875131.”

3. For **infrastructure, equipment and major results**, please add the EC emblem (flag) and the following sentence:

“This [infrastructure] [equipment] [insert type of result] is part of the eCharge4Drivers project. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 875131.”

7.5 External Interest Groups

A User Reference Group (URG) of experts will be established in order to have a wider base for gathering needs and requirements, define use cases and identify external EV charging options and relevant developments. An Observer Group of followers will promote the interaction with other vehicle manufacturers, CPOs, eMSPs and local authorities with a high interest and priority in adopting the project findings. POLIS will lead on the coordination of these groups.

Figure 11 Consortium relationship with the Expert Interest Groups

At the proposal stage, the following groups were interested in joining the External Interest Groups:

- Bilbao Council (OG/URG)
- Berlin Agency for e-mobility (EMO) (OG/URG)
- Gireve (OG/URG)
- Honda (OG)
- CREOS (General support - EIG not mentioned in the letter)
- Municipality of Bari (General support - EIG not mentioned in the letter)
- Metropolitan City of Bari (General support - EIG not mentioned in the letter)

7.5.1 Observer Group

The eCharge4Drivers Observer Group of followers will be established to promote interaction with other vehicle manufacturers, CPOs, eMSPs and local authorities with a high interest and priority in adopting the project findings.

A group of 15-20 electromobility actors (CPOs, eMSPs, Authorities, Grid actors, vehicle manufacturers), the so-called Observer Group, will benefit from a tailored plan, supporting their replication activities, including technical visits, interactive workshops and customised feedback on the potential replicability of the innovative products, services and solutions developed within the project.

HONDA R&D Europe GmbH and GIREVE, a major eRoaming platform, have already expressed their interest to join this Group. Other interested stakeholders will be selected through an open call launched by POLIS.

Although the Grant Agreement foresees 10 members, we will include more stakeholders in the database. In accordance with their interest and priorities, not more than 10 members of the

OG will be invited to a specific workshop. In some cases, it will be less than 10, to also give an opportunity to the URG members to be present.

This call will be launched in M5 on the eCharge4Drivers' website and on partners' websites. The final selection will be made based on the following criteria to be included in the application:

- The main reason to join the OG
- The expected impact
- The topic/ the combination of topics of interest.

7.5.2 User Reference Group

The User Reference Group of experts will be established in order to have a wider base for gathering needs and requirements, define use cases and identify external EV charging options and relevant developments.

The main objective of the URG is to enlarge the assessment and validation of the eCharge4Drivers concepts and results through independent expert advice. The URG members will follow the evolution of the eCharge4Drivers activities, contribute to the project development and validate the project results. Through the URG assessments, the Consortium will be able to widen its results, adapting them better to the needs of end users, cities and authorities, service providers and operators.

The aim is to establish a balanced group of around 20 active members, who will follow the project's evolution, providing end-user feedback on work-in-progress. Members of the URG will be gathered from: local authorities, eMSPs, CPOs, Vehicle manufacturers, Energy Retailers / electric utilities, fleet managers and researchers.

Interested stakeholders will be identified by project partners and invited to join the URG through a direct invitation. In order to identify and involve members that are really interested in the topic, POLIS will circulate a form with some questions identifying their interest in specific topics and also asking them for their motivation and reason for joining.

A list of the most relevant organisations and people will be identified by the consortium. A list of URG members will be compiled in a separate file named (URG Members), located in the Redmine SharePoint.

Criteria used for the URG

The selection criteria to be used for deciding which stakeholders will participate in the User Reference Group.

General evaluation criteria

Some aspects that will be considered across the different subgroups are:

- The relation of the stakeholder's activities with the deployment of Charging EV Infrastructure
- Geographical distribution
- Population / size and Urban extent (Applicable for Public authorities)
- Level of EV deployment in the area of activity
- Experience in specific topics related to electromobility
- Interest in specific topics related to electromobility
- Challenges faced related to the deployment of electromobility

Once the form has been circulated and different organisations have reached out to show their interest in participating in the URG, a matrix will be created following the mentioned criteria and a list of 20 members will be selected to form the URG.

7.5.3 Activity Plan for External Interest Groups

In total eight events will take place. The table below proposes initial planning for each type of activity. In the most of the cases two types of activities will be combined: physical workshop and technical visit to a demonstration site. Location and period for the planned activities will be fully aligned with the demonstration activities in WP5 and therefore are subject to changes.

Nr workshop	Type of Activity	Location (subject to changes)	Period (subject to changes)	OG/URG	Aim
1	Feedback workshop	Potentially location of the 3 rd GA	M11-12	URG	To provide feedback on the findings of the data collected in WP1 (T1.2) and to feed WP2 (T2.1 and T2.3)
Metropolitan areas					
2	Workshop and Technical and technical visit	Barcelona	M30 – M40	OG/URG (with more focus on OG representatives)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Assessing the extent in which eCharge4Drivers' DEMO solution has the potential for a successful roll-out -Assessing the support for further roll-outs -Obtaining feedback on the potential for replicability
3	Workshop and technical visit	Bari	M30 – 40	OG/URG (with more focus on OG representatives)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Assessing the extent eCharge4Drivers DEMO solution has the potential for a successful roll-out -Assessing the support for further roll-outs -Obtaining feedback on the potential for replicability
4	Workshop and Technical Visit and technical visit	Berlin	M30 – 40	OG/URG (with more focus on OG representatives)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Assessing the extent to which eCharge4Drivers' DEMO solution has the potential for a successful roll-out -Assessing the support for further roll-outs -Obtaining feedback on the potential for replicability
Nationwide					
5	Workshop and Technical Visit and technical visit	Austria	M30 – 40	OG/URG (with more focus on OG representatives)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assessing the extent to which eCharge4Drivers' DEMO solution has the potential for a successful roll-out -Assessing the support for further roll-outs

Nr workshop	Type of Activity	Location (subject to changes)	Period (subject to changes)	OG/URG	Aim
					-Obtaining feedback on the potential for replicability
6	Workshop and technical visit	Greece	M30 – 40	OG/URG (with more focus on OG representatives)	-Assessment of the extent eCharge4Drivers DEMO solution has the potential for a successful roll-out -Assessing the support for further roll-outs -Obtain feedback on the potential for replicability
7	Workshop and technical visit	Turkey	M30 – 40	OG/URG (with more focus on OG representatives)	- Assessing the extent to which eCharge4Drivers' DEMO solution has the potential for a successful roll-out -Assessing the support for further roll-outs -Obtaining feedback on the potential for replicability
8	Feedback workshop	Brussels/Athens	M40	OG/URG	Final validation of results together

Table 5 Activity Plan for eCharge4Drivers External Interests Groups

As indicated in the table above, a number of workshops will be focusing on the nationwide approach, while others will be approached from a perspective of the metropolitan areas. In addition to that, the meetings for the EIGs will also have a topical approach and will be further planned once there is a detailed planning of the demos in WP5.

The proposed topics at this initial stage are:

1. Advanced charging stations.
2. Alternative charging (Mobile charging, battery swapping, lamppost charging)
3. Standardisation and interfaces
4. Interoperable and user-centric services.

8 MONITORING IMPACT

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been established for eCharge4Drivers already during the proposal stages. These KPIs will be collected and evaluated to monitor and enhance the performance and outreach of the project and that for online media, press coverage and events. The registration of the activities will be done right after these have taken place in the database that has been created for this purpose. The actual monitoring evaluation will be done during the official reporting in M18 and M36.

Activity	Expected performance	
Activity	KPI target: Year 2	KPI target: Year 4
Website – number of visitors	200/month	400/month
Twitter – number of followers	100	200
LinkedIn – number of followers	100	200
Newsletter – number of newsletters sent out	2/year	2/year
Quantity of media coverage achieved	≥10	≥40
Number of peer reviewed publications	≥2	≥9
Number of external stakeholders attending the local events	20	-
Number of final event attendees	-	100-150
Number of participants in awareness events	≥20	≥20
Number of External Interest Groups participants	≥20	≥40
Number of projects contacted	≥5	≥10
Number of liaison activities performed	≥5	≥10

Table 6 eCharge4Drivers Dissemination Key Performance Indicators

Table 7 Preliminary Communication and Dissemination activities Gantt chart

9 CONCLUSION

The Communication and Dissemination Plan has identified and described the target groups for dissemination activities and highlighted how and through which dissemination channels they will be reached. It described the main dissemination tools, which will be particularly important for outreach activities. This strategy has also identified key initiatives and EU-funded projects to establish strategic alliances and collaboration mechanisms and defined the methodology for the establishment of the external interest groups that will play an important role in the transferability of the obtained results.

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